

SIMULATION OF THERMO-MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR DURING QUENCHING PROCESS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, a numerical model is presented which aims to simulate the occurrence and evolution of residual stresses during quenching process of metal matrix composites. Because the residual stresses on the interface are related to void formation, growth and coalescence, it is important to consider the variation of temperature, phase transformation and stress fields in a quenching process. Here, a set of coupled equations of the heat conduction, stress/strain and phase transformation of materials is given in the framework of metallo-thermo-mechanical theory. A method of numerical calculation by the finite element method considered the coupling of the thermo-mechanical behavior incorporating the variation of temperature, phase transformation and elastic-plastic deformation. As an example, simulation of a quenching process associated with a metal matrix composites of Ti-Fe matrix reinforced unidirectionally by SiC-ZrO₂ fiber is engaged in this study. In results of this simulation, the micro-structure behavior and residual stress on the interface of the fiber-matrix is evaluated, and the effect of fiber size is also discussed.

KEYWORDS: metallo-thermo-mechanical theory, interface behavior, metal matrix composites, quenching process, inelastic constitutive equation, jump conditions, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

In the heat treatment process of metallic material, such as quenching and tempering, complicated coupling effect of material behavior is sometimes important to be taken into account in the computer simulation. Metallo-thermo-mechanical theory[1-4] and some numerical method[5-7] capable to describing such interaction among phase transformation, effect of coupling between temperature, micro structure change due to phase transformation had been developed by many researchers based on continuum thermodynamics.

Recently, the development of some metal matrix composites depends strongly on controlling the physical and chemical properties at the fiber-matrix interface which are utilized by quenching process. However, because the residual stresses on the interface are related to void formation, growth and coalescence[8], it is important to consider the variation of temperature, phase transformation and stress fields in the quenching process. Here, in order to forecast thermo-mechanical behavior, three basic problems have to be considered. The first one is that phase transformation is strongly nonlinear with respect to time and location and it affects the mechanical behavior on the interface of the matrix composites. The second is the effect of size rate between the fiber and matrix composites; and the third is the jump of about

temperature, stress/strain fields on the interface due to variation of material properties in the fiber and matrix composites. For solving these problems, here, a set of coupled equations of heat conduction, stress/strain and phase transformation of materials is given in the framework of metallo-thermo-mechanical theory. A numerical model is presented which aims to simulate the occurrence and the evolution of residual stresses during the quenching process of metal matrix composites. The method of numerical calculation by the finite element method is considered for coupling the thermo-mechanical behavior incorporating the variation of temperature, phase transformation and stress/strain fields. In the calculation for stresses, an elastic-plastic and creep constitutive model is employed. As an example of calculation, simulation of a quenching process associated with a Ti-Fe alloy reinforced unidirectionally by SiC-ZrO₂ fiber is engaged in this research. In results of this simulation, thermo-mechanical behavior and the residual stresses of the composites is evaluated, and some effect due to fiber-matrix size are also presented.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The detail of introducing the governing equations in the framework of thermodynamics capable of describing the governing equations for temperature and stress/strain fields incorporating metallic structures are already reported elsewhere[5]. Here, the fundamental equations are summarized in the following:

Mixture rule

When a material point undergoing a heat treatment process is assumed to be composed of multi-phase structure, an assumption is made that a material parameters χ is described by the mixture law[9]

$$\chi = \sum_{I=1}^N \chi_I \xi_I; \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{I=1}^N \xi_I = 1, \quad (1)$$

where ξ_I denote the volume fraction for the I-th phase.

Heat Conduction Equations

The local energy balance or the first law of thermodynamics is usually given in terms of the internal energy $e = g + T \eta + (\sigma_{ij} \epsilon_{ij}) / \rho$, as

$$\rho \dot{e} = \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} - \frac{\partial h_i}{\partial x_i}, \quad (2)$$

with stress power $\sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$. Here, ρ and h_i are the density and heat flux, respectively. η is the entropy of the thermodynamic state. Introducing the expressions for specific heat $c = T(\partial \eta / \partial T)$, Equation (2) is reduced to a heat conduction equation

$$\rho c \dot{T} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right) - \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^p + \sum \rho_I l_I \dot{\xi}_I = 0, \quad (3)$$

where k and l_I denote the coefficient of heat conduction and the latent heat produced by the progressive I-th constituent.

The boundary conditions of heat transfer on the inner surface is assumed to be

$$-k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} n_i = h(T - T_w), \quad (4)$$

where h and T_w are the heat transfer coefficient and the temperature of coolant on heat transfer boundary with unit normal n_i , respectively.

Constitutive Equation

Total strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ is assumed to be divided into elastic, plastic, thermal strain rates and those by structural dilatation due to phase transformation and creep such that

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^e + \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^p + \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^T + \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^m + \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^c . \quad (5)$$

Here, elastic and thermal strains are normally expressed as

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^e = \frac{1+\nu}{E} \sigma_{ij} - \frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{kk} \delta_{ij} , \quad (6)$$

and

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^T = \alpha(T - T_0) \delta_{ij} , \quad (7)$$

with Young's modulus E , Poisson's ratio ν and thermal expansion coefficient α , respectively. Here, T_0 is the initial temperature of material.

Strain rates due to structural dilatation and transformation plasticity depending on the I -th constituent read

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^m = \sum_{I=1}^N \beta_I \xi_I \delta_{ij} , \quad (8)$$

where β stands for the dilatation due to structural change.

The plastic strain rate is reduced to the form when employing temperature dependent materials parameters

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^p = \lambda \frac{\partial F}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} = \hat{G} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \sigma_{kl}} \dot{\sigma}_{kl} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial T} \dot{T} + \sum_{I=1}^N \frac{\partial F}{\partial \xi_I} \dot{\xi}_I \right) \frac{\partial F}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} , \quad (9)$$

with a temperature dependent yield function

$$F = F(\sigma_{ij}, \varepsilon^p, \kappa, T, \xi_I) , \quad (10)$$

with hardening parameter κ , where

$$\frac{1}{\hat{G}} = - \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \varepsilon_{mn}^p} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \kappa} \sigma_{mn} \right) \frac{\partial F}{\partial \sigma_{mn}} , \quad (11)$$

The creep strain rate is assumed to follow a simple Norton creep law as

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^c = \frac{3}{2} A_c^{1/m} \bar{\sigma}^{(n-m)/m} \bar{\varepsilon}^{c(m-1)/m} s_{ij} . \quad (12)$$

Here, s_{ij} , $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}$ are deviatoric stress, equivalent stress and equivalent strain, respectively. Either isotropic or kinetic hardening type of yield function F is available to be used in the paper. Symbol A_c , n and m are material parameters based on Norton creep law. Either isotropic or kinetic hardening type of yield function F is available to be used in this paper.

Kinetics of Quenching Process

In the case of quenching, two kinds of phase transformation are anticipated: One is governed by the diffusionless or martensite mechanism. From thermodynamic consideration, the formula for this type of reaction from austenite is assumed to be governed by the modified Magee's rule[10] as

$$\xi_M = 1 - \exp[\phi(T - T_M) - \varphi(\sigma_{ij})] , \quad (13)$$

with

$$\varphi(\sigma_{ij}) = A_1 \sigma_m + A_2 J_2^{1/2} , \quad (14)$$

where T_M is the martensite-start temperature under vanishing stress. The parameters A_1 and A_2 can be identified if we have the data of the martensitic transformation depending on the applied stress.

The other type of phase transformation is controlled by diffusion mechanism, and the volume fraction of developing phase such as pearlite may be expressed by modifying the Johnson-Mehl relation[11] as

$$\xi_p = 1 - \exp(-V_e) \quad , \quad (15)$$

where V_e is defined by

$$V_e = \int_0^t \bar{f}(T, \sigma_{ij})(t - \tau)^3 d\tau \quad . \quad (16)$$

Here, we separate the function $\bar{f}(T, \sigma_{ij})$ into two independent function of temperature and stress as

$$\bar{f}(T, \sigma_{ij}) = f_1(T) f_2(\sigma_{ij}) \quad . \quad (17)$$

Since the time-temperature-transformation TTT diagram under the applied mean stress σ_m in logarithmic scale deviates from the one without stress which is represented by the function $f(T)$, the kinetic equation of diffusion type is often applied to the variations of pearlite or ferrite structure in quenching processes. An identification of the function $f(T)$ can be made possible by the use of some experimental data of the structure change.

JUMP CONDITIONS ON INTERFACE

Due to difference of materials behavior between the fiber and matrix composites, discontinuous phenomenon of thermomechanical fields on the interface of MMC materials during the quenching process will be presented. In order to describe the discontinuous phenomenon, some jump conditions can usually be used. If the interface of materials does not propagate within the domain, the conservation laws of mass, momentum and energy are respectively shown as[12]

$$[q] = 0 \quad ; \quad [\dot{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{n}] = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad [\mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{n}] = 0 \quad , \quad (18)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ and \mathbf{t} indicate the displacement vector and stress vector on the interface surface. \mathbf{n} means the outward normal from the region (-) to the region (+) on the surface of the interface. The function $[\psi]$ represents the jump of a physical quantity ψ between the two domains over the interface, i.e.

$$[\psi] = \psi^+ - \psi^- \quad . \quad (19)$$

The discontinuity in the macroscopic sense take advantage from the phenomenological point of view when we deal with the thermo-mechanical behavior of structures involving imperfect interface.

ALGORITHM OF FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The formulated finite element equation system considering the coupling between increment of nodal displacement $\{\Delta u\}$ and temperature $\{T\}$ as well as volume fraction of structure ξ_I can be expressed as

$$[P]\{\dot{T}\} + [H]\{T\} = \{Q(\xi_I), \sigma_{ij}\} \quad (20)$$

and

$$[K(u_i)]\{\Delta u_i\} = \{\Delta F(T, \xi_I)\} \quad (21)$$

Here, matrices $[P]$, $[H]$ and $[K]$ represent the matrices of heat capacity, heat conduction and stiffness, respectively, and the vectors $\{Q\}$ and $\{\Delta F\}$ are heat flux, and increments of thermal load. These equations are strong nonlinear equation, which are derived by the use of the expression of stress increment vector as

$$\{d\sigma\} = [D] \left(\{d\varepsilon\} - \frac{3d\bar{\varepsilon}^c}{2\bar{\sigma}} \{s\} - \{\bar{\alpha}\}dT - \sum_{I=1}^N \{\bar{\beta}\}d\xi_I \right) + \frac{1}{S_0} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}^2}{\partial T} dT + \sum_{I=1}^N \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}^2}{\partial \xi_I} d\xi_I \right) \{s\} , \quad (22)$$

where $\bar{\varepsilon}^c$ and $\{s\}$ are equivalent creep strain and deviatoric stress vector. $[D]$ denote a elastic-plastic matrix based on Mises' type yield function. Here, the functions depending on temperature and phase transformation $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ can be written as

$$\{\bar{\alpha}\} = \frac{\partial}{\partial T} ([D^e]^{-1} \{\sigma\}) + \sum_{I=1}^N (\alpha_I \xi_I \{1\} + \frac{\partial \alpha_I}{\partial T} \xi_I dT \{1\}) , \quad (23)$$

and
$$\{\bar{\beta}\} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_I} ([D^e]^{-1} \{\sigma\}) + \beta_I \{1\} , \quad (24)$$

α_I and β_I are the coefficients of thermal expansion and dilatation due to I-th phase transformation, respectively. $[D^e]$ denote the elastic matrix of materials.

In order to treat unsteady coupled equations depending on time, a time integration scheme 'step-by-step time integration method' is introduced in numerical calculation, while an incremental method[13] is used for deformation and stress analysis.

In order to treat the physical discontinuity, a penalty function method[14] or Lagrangian multiplier method was employed in this paper.

SIMULATED RESULTS

Model of Simulation

The material for simulation of quenching process was a metal matrix composite reinforced unidirectionally with continuous fibers. The matrix material was a Ti-Fe alloy (• type) consisting of Ti-3.25Fe-2Cr-2Mo in weight percent. The reinforcing phase was continuous SiC-ZrO₂ fiber. The diameter of fibers is 300μm. It is assumed that the fiber is located periodically with the same interval and that each fiber is the same shape as shown in Fig.1(a). Then, the unit cell including a fiber depicted by broken line in Fig.1(a) is extracted from the bulk material. For the sake of simplification, a unit cell is considered as plane strain problem as indicated in Fig.1(b). In order to examine the effect of fiber size, three ratios of the radius of fiber to the width of matrix are considered with r/a=1/3 and 2/3. The quenching process of the model is started from an initial temperature at 850 °C (temperature of oil 60 °C). The heat transfer coefficient to oil on the surface of the composites is chosen as h=0.00235cal/(mm²·s·°C). As for the finite element calculation of temperature and stress fields based on the obtained mixture rule of the phase transformations, the following material table are employed:

Table 1 Parameters for finite element analysis

	Matrix	Fiber
Heat conductivity [cal/mm s deg]	0.0361+0.0000193T	0.0289-0.0000128T
Density [g/cm ³]	7.84	3.18
Specific heat [cal/(g deg)]	0.286	0.219
Young's modulus [Gpa]	220.0+0.054T-0.00032T ²	398.4+0.039T-0.00028T ²
Poisson's ratio	0.32	0.19
Thermal expansion [1/deg]	0.518x10 ⁻⁵	0.31x10 ⁻⁵
Dilatation of phase transformation [%]	β _M =-0.015; β _P =-0.011	~
Yield stress [Mpa]	526.5-0.12T-0.00045T ²	780.0-0.16T-0.00049T ²
Hardening coefficient [Mpa]	238.2-0.225T	361.5-0.29T

Fig. 1 Cross section of metal matrix composite and unit cell model.

RESULTS OF SIMULATION

Figure 2(a) and (b) show the variation of temperature distribution on the center of the fiber and the surface of matrix corner. The volume fraction of martensite transformation at $t=0.125(\text{sec})$ for the two size ratio are shown in Fig.3. The equivalent stress at $t=0.125$ and $0.25(\text{sec})$ are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5. Figure 6 shows the residual equivalent stress with different size ratio. From these results, we can observe that the temperature variation of composites of these two size ratio are nearly similar, but the distribution of martensite transformation near the interface has different form. When martensite transformation produced on the interface for the small size ratio ($r/a=1/3$), i.e. $t=0.125(\text{sec})$, distribution of the equivalent stress which is shown in Fig.4 exhibits jump phenomenon. However, jump behavior done not appear in the case of large size (ratio $r/a=2/3$). The jump of equivalent stress with small size ratio is remains until to finish of the quenching process.

On the interface region with small size ratio, the jump level of equivalent stress is also very small, but the rapid variation of equivalent stress appears in the finished domain of martensite. Due to high elastic modulus of the fibers and inelastic region in finished domain of martensite, a harmonious distribution of stress in fiber in the case of a small size ratio can be expected.

(a) $r/a = 1/3$

(b) $r/a = 2/3$

Fig.2 Temperature variation on center of fiber and surface of matrix corner.

(a) $r/a=1/3$

(b) $r/a=2/3$

Fig.3 Distribution of martensite fraction at $t=0.125$ (sec).

(a) $r/a = 1/3$

(b) $r/a = 2/3$

Fig.4 Distribution of equivalent stress at $t = 0.125$ (sec).

(a) $r/a = 1/3$ (b) $r/a = 2/3$
 Fig.5 Distribution of equivalent stress at $t = 0.25$ (sec).

(a) $r/a = 1/3$ (b) $r/a = 2/3$
 Fig.6 Distribution of residual equivalent stress.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Metallo-thermo-mechanical theory previously developed is extended to simulated the quenching process. By adopting this theory, finite element simulation of a unit cell of metal matrix composites is carried out, and some results of the calculated distribution of temperature and residual stress are discussed. From these results, we can obtain some useful conclusions:

- (1) Simulated results of temperature and stresses during and after quenching process based on coupled analysis present thermomechanical behavior on the interface of the MMC composites.
- (2) Micro-mechanism of quenching including structure change depending on temperature and inelastic effect on stress hardening due to martensite transformation is revealed to be reasonable.
- (3) Effect of size rate of fiber and matrix is presented and it is important to select the size ratio for a perfect design of MMC composites.

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